

Inference of Cross-Species Gene Flow Using Genomic data Depends on the Methods: Case Study of Gene Flow in *Drosophila*

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SI TEXT.

BAYESIAN PARAMETER ESTIMATION IN DATA SIMULATED USING THE QUARTET TREES OF FIGURE 2

We used the MSC-M and MSC-I models for four species (A, B, C , and outgroup O) of Figure 2, with gene flow between non-sister lineages (B, C), to simulate replicate datasets, each analyzed using BPP under both the MSC-M and MSC-I models, resulting in eight simulation-analysis settings. In the main text, we have discussed Bayesian estimation of the rate of gene flow (φ in MSC-I and M in MSC-M), summarized in Figure 4, as well as Bayesian test of gene flow (Fig. 5). Here we discuss estimation of all parameters in the model, summarized in Figures S4–S11.

In the M-M settings (Figs. S4 & S8), data were simulated under MSC-M and analyzed under the same model so that the correct model of gene flow was specified. Similarly under the I-I settings (Figs. S6 & S10), the MSC-I model was used to both simulate and analyze data. These represent the best-case scenarios and provide a reference for comparison. In all cases, species divergence times (τ_R, τ_S, τ_T) were very well estimated, as were population sizes for extant species ($\theta_A, \theta_B, \theta_C, \theta_O$). In the I-I setting, the introgression time ($\tau_X = \tau_Y$ in Fig. 2b & d) was well-estimated as well. The posterior means approach the true values while the 95% HPD CIs become narrower when the data size increases. The results were consistent with the asymptotic expectation that the CI width should reduce by a half when the number of loci quadruples ($L = 250$ versus 1000) (O'Hagan and Forster, 2004, p.73). In informative datasets, the coverage of the 95% CI was in general higher than 95%. Ancestral population sizes ($\theta_R, \theta_S, \theta_T$) had larger uncertainties, especially at the low mutation rate ($\theta = 0.0025$) and in small datasets (with 250 loci and 250 sites), as did φ in MSC-I or M in MSC-M. Note that in our simulation, species divergence times (τ_s) are proportional to θ so that the two values of θ mimic the use of genome regions with different mutation rates. The patterns are consistent with previous simulations conducted under the MSC and MSC-I models (Huang *et al.*, 2020). Introgression probability was more precisely estimated in the inflow model (with gene flow from the outgroup species C to the ingroup species B , Fig. 2a&b) than in the outflow model (with gene flow from the ingroup species B to the outgroup species C , Fig. 2c&d) (Fig. S6 inflow I-I vs. Fig. S10 outflow I-I). For example, the CI width in the least informative data set ($L = 250, S = 2, n = 250, \theta = 0.0025$) was ~43% narrower under the inflow than outflow models. These results are consistent with the observation of Thawornwattana *et al.* (2023).

In the M-I settings (Figs. S5 for inflow-M-I & S9 for outflow-M-I), data were simulated under MSC-M and analyzed under MSC-I, so that the mode of gene flow was misspecified. The analysis of Huang *et al.* (2022) suggests that when data are generated under MSC-M but analyzed under MSC-I, not all gene flow that has occurred is recoverable, and the estimated amount under MSC-I ($\hat{\varphi}$) is less than the expected amount (φ_0) given by eq. 2, with $\hat{\varphi} < \varphi_0$. This was indeed the case in the simulation here (Figs. 4, inflow M-I and outflow M-I). The underestimation was more serious (with larger difference between $\hat{\varphi}$ and φ_0) in the outflow case than in the inflow case, and for short sequences ($n = 250$) than for long sequences ($n = 1000$). While gene flow occurs throughout the time period ($0, \tau_T$) (Fig. 2a&c), the estimated introgression time ($\hat{\tau}_X$) was smaller than the mid-time ($\tau_T/2$) and closer to the end of the time period (0), in particular, for datasets with many sequences per species ($S = 8$ versus 2) and for long sequences ($n = 1000$ versus 250) (Figs. S5 & S9). This is because the estimated introgression time is dominated by the most recent sequence divergence time between species (Huang *et al.*, 2022). Among parameters present in both the MSC-M and MSC-I models, species divergence times were accurately estimated except for τ_S which showed a small negative

bias (Figs. S5 & S9). Population sizes for extant and ancestral species were well-estimated as well, although there seemed to be a small positive bias in θ_5 . Overall estimates of shared parameters were very similar to those in the I-I setting where there was no model misspecification.

In the I-M settings (Figs. S7 & S11), data were simulated under MSC-I and analyzed under MSC-M. The estimated migration rate under MSC-M ($\hat{M}$) was less than the predicted rate under the true MSC-I model (M_0), with $\hat{M} < M_0$ (Figs. S7 for inflow-I-M and Fig. S11 for outflow-I-M). Thus not all gene flow that occurred according to the true MSC-I model was recovered by the misspecified MSC-M model. Again, parameters common in both models, including species divergence times and population sizes for extant and ancestral species, were accurately estimated with little bias (Figs. S7 & S11). There was no discernible difference from estimates in the M-M setting in which there was no model misspecification.

Whilst the MSC-M and MSC-I models make very different assumptions about the mode of gene flow, in the simulation settings examined here (Figs. S4–S11), both produced reliable estimates of divergence times and population sizes even when the mode of gene flow was misspecified.

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Fig. S1: Model of gene flow for clade 2 inferred by Suvorov et al. (2022, Fig. 3). The fractions next to each arrow represent the number of species triplets that support the introgression event by both DCT and BLT out of the number of informative triplets tested (table S1).

Fig. S2: Posterior means (points) and 95% HPD CIs (bars) for τ and θ s in the final model of figure 1b in BPP analysis of the *Drosophila* data under the JC (Jukes and Cantor, 1969) and GTR (Tavaré, 1986; Yang, 1994) mutation models.

Fig. S3: The impact of priors on τ and θ in BPP analysis of the data simulated using parameter estimates from the *Drosophila* data (Tables S2 & S3, *D. insularis* outgroup, first half). We used three sets of priors on τ and θ , with the prior means to be (i) equal to the true values (the 1x prior): $\tau_r \sim G(2, 50)$ and $\theta \sim G(2, 200)$; (ii) 10x smaller than the true values (the 0.1x prior): $\tau_r \sim G(2, 500)$ and $\theta \sim G(2, 2000)$; or (iii) 10x larger (the 10x prior): $\tau_r \sim G(2, 5)$ and $\theta \sim G(2, 20)$. Estimates of introgression probabilities and migration rates are in table S9. Estimates for all parameters under the 1x prior are in table S8.

Fig. S4: (inflow-M-M) Posterior means and 95% HPD CIs for parameters in BPP analysis of replicate datasets simulated and analyzed under the inflow migration (MSC-M) model of figure 2a. Solid black lines represent true values. Numbers above (or below) the CI bars are the coverage probability. We use the ‘simulation-analysis’ format to specify our simulation setting, so that ‘M-M’ means that data were both simulated and analyzed under the MSC-M model, while ‘M-I’ (Fig. S5) means that data were simulated under the MSC-M model and analyzed under the MSC-I model.

Fig. S5: (inflow-M-I) Posterior means and 95% HPD CIs for parameters in **BPP** analysis of datasets simulated under the inflow migration ('M' for MSC-M) model (Fig. 2a) and analyzed under the introgression ('I' for MSC-I) model (Fig. 2b). Dashed black lines for the φ parameter denote the theoretical value given by eq. 2. See legend to figure S4.

Fig. S6: (inflow-I-I). See legends to figures [S4](#) & [S5](#).

Fig. S7: (inflow-I-M). See legends to figures [S4](#)&[S5](#).

Fig. S8: (outflow-M-M). See legends to figures [S4](#)&[S5](#).

Fig. S9: (outflow-M-I). See legends to figures [S4](#) & [S5](#).

Fig. S10: (outflow-I-I). See legends to figures [S4](#)&[S5](#).

Fig. S11: (outflow-I-M). See legends to figures [S4](#)&[S5](#).

Table S1: Fraction of species triplets that supported gene flow out of all informative triplets tested using DCT/BLT for the 11 *Drosophila* species of clade 2 (from Suvorov et al. 2022, Supplementary Data S2)

	<i>subobscura</i>	<i>guanche</i>	<i>obscura</i>	<i>bifasciata</i>	<i>pseudoobscura</i>	<i>persimilis</i>	<i>miranda</i>	<i>lowei</i>	<i>azteca</i>	<i>athabasca</i>
<i>D. subobscura</i>	–									
<i>D. guanche</i>	–									
<i>D. obscura</i>	0/1	0/1								
<i>D. bifasciata</i>	–	–	–							
<i>D. pseudoobscura</i>	0/3	0/3	2/5	2/2						
<i>D. persimilis</i>	0/3	0/3	2/4	–	–					
<i>D. miranda</i>	0/4	0/4	2/8	2/6	0/1	–				
<i>D. lowei</i>	1/6	1/5	3/9	3/8	–	–	0/2			
<i>D. azteca</i>	0/1	0/1	2/3	2/2	0/3	0/1	0/2	1/4		
<i>D. athabasca</i>	0/3	0/2	2/4	2/4	0/2	0/1	0/4	0/4	0/1	
<i>D. affinis</i>	–	–	2/3	2/2	0/1	–	0/2	2/3	–	–

Table S2: The impact of outgroup. Posterior means and 95% HPD CIs for parameters under the MSC-I models obtained from BPP analyses of the *Drosophila* data including an outgroup

Parameters	Outgroup = <i>D. insularis</i>		Outgroup = <i>D. melanogaster</i>	
	First half	Second half	First half	Second half
Population sizes (θ , $\times 10^{-2}$)				
θ_o	17.95 (17.08, 18.84)	17.99 (17.09, 18.92)	16.96 (16.21, 17.72)	17.15 (16.37, 17.94)
θ_r	11.39 (10.05, 12.73)	11.87 (10.70, 13.07)	1.38 (0.16, 2.91)	1.77 (0.12, 4.02)
θ_a	5.14 (4.89, 5.39)	5.22 (4.97, 5.47)	5.06 (4.83, 5.29)	5.26 (5.02, 5.50)
θ_b	7.20 (6.79, 7.61)	7.86 (7.41, 8.31)	7.01 (6.61, 7.40)	7.80 (7.37, 8.24)
θ_c	4.50 (3.73, 5.27)	3.65 (3.06, 4.26)	4.35 (3.65, 5.06)	3.95 (3.32, 4.61)
θ_d	1.72 (1.62, 1.83)	1.78 (1.67, 1.88)	1.74 (1.64, 1.84)	1.78 (1.67, 1.89)
θ_e	3.72 (3.49, 3.96)	3.69 (3.45, 3.93)	3.70 (3.47, 3.94)	3.71 (3.47, 3.95)
θ_f	1.57 (1.46, 1.67)	1.57 (1.47, 1.68)	1.58 (1.48, 1.68)	1.58 (1.47, 1.68)
θ_g	1.11 (0.97, 1.25)	1.11 (0.97, 1.26)	1.11 (0.97, 1.25)	1.13 (0.98, 1.28)
θ_h	1.92 (1.78, 2.06)	1.89 (1.75, 2.03)	1.92 (1.78, 2.07)	1.90 (1.75, 2.03)
θ_i	1.46 (1.22, 1.69)	1.31 (1.08, 1.56)	1.48 (1.25, 1.72)	1.33 (1.09, 1.58)
θ_w	= θ_a	= θ_a	= θ_a	= θ_a
θ_z	= θ_b	= θ_b	= θ_b	= θ_b
θ_x	= θ_c	= θ_c	= θ_c	= θ_c
θ_y	= θ_b	= θ_b	= θ_b	= θ_b
Speciation/introgression times (τ , $\times 10^{-2}$)				
τ_o	9.54 (9.33, 9.76)	10.05 (9.84, 10.26)	7.48 (7.35, 7.61)	7.90 (7.76, 8.04)
τ_r	7.53 (7.14, 8.00)	7.43 (7.09, 7.82)	7.42 (7.27, 7.57)	7.84 (7.67, 8.02)
τ_a	2.75 (2.71, 2.78)	2.74 (2.70, 2.78)	2.78 (2.74, 2.82)	2.78 (2.74, 2.82)
τ_b	2.18 (2.15, 2.21)	2.17 (2.14, 2.20)	2.23 (2.19, 2.26)	2.18 (2.15, 2.22)
τ_c	1.96 (1.89, 2.04)	2.07 (2.01, 2.13)	1.98 (1.91, 2.05)	2.06 (1.99, 2.12)
τ_d	1.03 (1.00, 1.05)	1.01 (0.99, 1.03)	1.03 (1.01, 1.05)	1.01 (0.99, 1.03)
τ_e	1.01 (0.98, 1.04)	1.03 (1.00, 1.06)	1.02 (0.99, 1.05)	1.03 (1.00, 1.06)
τ_f	0.75 (0.72, 0.77)	0.77 (0.74, 0.79)	0.75 (0.72, 0.77)	0.77 (0.75, 0.80)
τ_g	0.63 (0.60, 0.65)	0.63 (0.60, 0.65)	0.63 (0.61, 0.66)	0.62 (0.60, 0.65)
τ_h	0.41 (0.39, 0.43)	0.40 (0.38, 0.42)	0.42 (0.40, 0.43)	0.40 (0.38, 0.42)
τ_i	0.15 (0.13, 0.17)	0.18 (0.16, 0.21)	0.15 (0.13, 0.17)	0.18 (0.16, 0.20)
$\tau_w = \tau_z = \tau_{w \rightarrow z}$	4.00 (3.92, 4.09)	3.98 (3.92, 4.03)	3.98 (3.89, 4.07)	4.05 (3.99, 4.11)
$\tau_x = \tau_y = \tau_{x \rightarrow y}$	2.73 (2.69, 2.77)	2.72 (2.68, 2.77)	2.77 (2.72, 2.81)	2.77 (2.72, 2.81)
Introgression probabilities				
$ra \rightarrow rb$ (or $w \rightarrow z$)	0.708 (0.670, 0.747)	0.677 (0.640, 0.718)	0.672 (0.641, 0.703)	0.697 (0.665, 0.730)
$ac \rightarrow rb$ (or $x \rightarrow y$)	0.098 (0.080, 0.117)	0.080 (0.066, 0.094)	0.085 (0.067, 0.105)	0.083 (0.068, 0.097)

Note.— The outgroup species is either *D. insularis* or *D. melanogaster*, with the latter being a closer outgroup for clade 2 (Suvorov *et al.*, 2022, Fig. 1). Node *r* is the root for clade 2 (Fig. 1b), and *o* is the root of the tree including the outgroup. Note that *D. insularis* is a more distant outgroup to clade 2 (with a larger τ_o) than is *D. melanogaster*. The estimates for the first half with the *D. insularis* outgroup are used to simulate data analyzed in table S8.

Table S3: The impact of the outgroup. Pposterior means and 95% HPD CIs (in parentheses) under the MSC-M models obtained from BPP analyses of *Drosophila* data including an outgroup

Parameters	Outgroup = <i>D. insularis</i>		Outgroup = <i>D. melanogaster</i>	
	First half	Second half	First half	Second half
Population sizes (θ , $\times 10^{-2}$)				
θ_o	18.06 (17.18, 19.01)	17.97 (17.07, 18.88)	16.66 (15.93, 17.43)	16.77 (15.98, 17.52)
θ_r	6.99 (0.26, 13.79)	12.71 (10.94, 14.55)	1.44 (0.15, 3.09)	1.51 (0.18, 3.25)
θ_a	4.81 (4.58, 5.04)	4.81 (4.60, 5.02)	4.65 (4.44, 4.85)	4.74 (4.54, 4.94)
θ_b	6.83 (6.44, 7.20)	7.59 (7.18, 7.99)	6.57 (6.22, 6.93)	7.36 (6.98, 7.76)
θ_c	4.55 (3.81, 5.35)	3.59 (3.04, 4.20)	4.27 (3.64, 4.98)	3.87 (3.28, 4.51)
θ_d	1.73 (1.63, 1.84)	1.78 (1.68, 1.89)	1.75 (1.65, 1.86)	1.79 (1.68, 1.90)
θ_e	3.72 (3.48, 3.95)	3.68 (3.44, 3.92)	3.71 (3.49, 3.95)	3.72 (3.49, 3.96)
θ_f	1.58 (1.48, 1.68)	1.58 (1.47, 1.68)	1.59 (1.48, 1.69)	1.58 (1.47, 1.68)
θ_g	1.10 (0.97, 1.25)	1.11 (0.97, 1.26)	1.10 (0.97, 1.24)	1.12 (0.98, 1.27)
θ_h	1.92 (1.78, 2.06)	1.88 (1.75, 2.02)	1.92 (1.78, 2.06)	1.89 (1.75, 2.03)
θ_i	1.46 (1.23, 1.69)	1.31 (1.08, 1.56)	1.47 (1.25, 1.72)	1.33 (1.09, 1.58)
Speciation/introgression times (τ , $\times 10^{-2}$)				
τ_o	9.51 (9.29, 9.73)	10.05 (9.85, 10.26)	7.61 (7.49, 7.75)	8.11 (7.97, 8.25)
τ_r	8.77 (7.75, 9.69)	8.34 (7.90, 8.74)	7.60 (7.46, 7.74)	8.10 (7.95, 8.24)
τ_a	2.74 (2.70, 2.78)	2.75 (2.71, 2.79)	2.80 (2.77, 2.84)	2.80 (2.76, 2.84)
τ_b	2.20 (2.17, 2.23)	2.18 (2.15, 2.22)	2.24 (2.21, 2.28)	2.20 (2.16, 2.24)
τ_c	1.95 (1.87, 2.02)	2.08 (2.02, 2.14)	1.99 (1.92, 2.05)	2.07 (2.00, 2.13)
τ_d	1.02 (1.00, 1.04)	1.01 (0.99, 1.03)	1.02 (1.00, 1.05)	1.01 (0.99, 1.03)
τ_e	1.01 (0.98, 1.04)	1.03 (1.00, 1.05)	1.02 (0.99, 1.05)	1.03 (1.00, 1.06)
τ_f	0.74 (0.72, 0.77)	0.77 (0.74, 0.79)	0.74 (0.72, 0.77)	0.77 (0.75, 0.80)
τ_g	0.63 (0.61, 0.66)	0.62 (0.60, 0.65)	0.63 (0.61, 0.66)	0.62 (0.60, 0.65)
τ_h	0.41 (0.39, 0.43)	0.40 (0.38, 0.42)	0.42 (0.40, 0.43)	0.40 (0.38, 0.42)
τ_i	0.15 (0.13, 0.17)	0.18 (0.16, 0.20)	0.15 (0.13, 0.17)	0.18 (0.16, 0.20)
Migration rates				
$ra \rightarrow rb$ (or $w \rightarrow z$)	0.557 (0.515, 0.603)	0.594 (0.549, 0.641)	0.531 (0.489, 0.574)	0.562 (0.516, 0.605)
$ac \rightarrow rb$ (or $x \rightarrow y$)	0.016 (0.003, 0.029)	0.009 (0.000, 0.020)	0.016 (0.004, 0.029)	0.021 (0.007, 0.036)

Note.— See Note in table S2. Node *o* is the root of the species tree including the outgroup. The estimates for the first half with the *D. insularis* outgroup are used to simulate data analyzed in table S8.

Table S4: Posterior means and 95% HPD CIs of parameters under the final MSC-I and MSC-M models of Figure 1b obtained from BPP analyses of the *Drosophila* data set

Parameters	MSC-I		MSC-M	
	First half	Second half	First half	Second half
Population sizes ($\theta, \times 10^{-2}$)				
θ_r	12.85 (11.95, 13.76)	14.47 (13.50, 15.46)	13.24 (12.22, 14.29)	14.86 (13.81, 15.92)
θ_a	5.19 (4.92, 5.46)	5.22 (4.98, 5.48)	4.62 (4.41, 4.82)	4.64 (4.44, 4.86)
θ_b	7.49 (7.03, 7.95)	8.16 (7.68, 8.65)	6.92 (6.51, 7.31)	7.74 (7.28, 8.19)
θ_c	5.28 (4.31, 6.30)	4.44 (3.64, 5.27)	5.16 (4.25, 6.09)	4.34 (3.60, 5.10)
θ_d	1.72 (1.62, 1.82)	1.77 (1.67, 1.88)	1.74 (1.64, 1.85)	1.79 (1.68, 1.89)
θ_e	3.78 (3.54, 4.02)	3.74 (3.50, 3.99)	3.79 (3.56, 4.03)	3.75 (3.51, 3.99)
θ_f	1.51 (1.41, 1.61)	1.48 (1.38, 1.58)	1.52 (1.42, 1.62)	1.49 (1.39, 1.59)
θ_g	1.09 (0.95, 1.23)	1.12 (0.97, 1.27)	1.09 (0.95, 1.23)	1.12 (0.97, 1.27)
θ_h	1.93 (1.78, 2.07)	1.88 (1.75, 2.02)	1.92 (1.78, 2.07)	1.88 (1.75, 2.02)
θ_i	1.46 (1.24, 1.70)	1.31 (1.07, 1.55)	1.46 (1.23, 1.70)	1.30 (1.06, 1.54)
θ_w	= θ_a	= θ_a	–	–
θ_z	= θ_b	= θ_b	–	–
θ_x	= θ_c	= θ_c	–	–
θ_y	= θ_b	= θ_b	–	–
Speciation/introgression times ($\tau, \times 10^{-2}$)				
τ_r	7.28 (6.89, 7.74)	7.42 (7.10, 7.73)	7.48 (6.93, 8.17)	7.61 (7.05, 8.25)
τ_a	2.58 (2.54, 2.62)	2.58 (2.54, 2.62)	2.60 (2.57, 2.64)	2.61 (2.57, 2.65)
τ_b	2.21 (2.18, 2.24)	2.19 (2.15, 2.22)	2.23 (2.19, 2.26)	2.21 (2.17, 2.25)
τ_c	1.85 (1.77, 1.94)	1.94 (1.88, 2.01)	1.86 (1.78, 1.93)	1.95 (1.89, 2.01)
τ_d	1.03 (1.01, 1.05)	1.01 (0.99, 1.04)	1.03 (1.01, 1.05)	1.01 (0.99, 1.03)
τ_e	1.02 (0.99, 1.05)	1.03 (1.00, 1.06)	1.02 (0.99, 1.05)	1.03 (1.00, 1.06)
τ_f	0.69 (0.67, 0.72)	0.73 (0.70, 0.75)	0.69 (0.66, 0.71)	0.72 (0.70, 0.75)
τ_g	0.63 (0.61, 0.66)	0.62 (0.59, 0.65)	0.63 (0.61, 0.66)	0.62 (0.59, 0.65)
τ_h	0.41 (0.39, 0.43)	0.40 (0.38, 0.42)	0.41 (0.39, 0.43)	0.40 (0.38, 0.42)
τ_i	0.15 (0.12, 0.17)	0.18 (0.16, 0.20)	0.15 (0.12, 0.17)	0.18 (0.16, 0.20)
$\tau_w = \tau_z = \tau_{w \rightarrow z}$	3.81 (3.75, 3.87)	3.88 (3.82, 3.94)	–	–
$\tau_x = \tau_y = \tau_{x \rightarrow y}$	2.57 (2.53, 2.61)	2.57 (2.53, 2.61)	–	–
Gene-flow rate				
	Introgression probability (φ)		Migration rate (M)	
$ra \rightarrow rb$ (or $w \rightarrow z$)	0.728 (0.689, 0.769)	0.712 (0.681, 0.743)	0.568 (0.518, 0.615)	0.603 (0.555, 0.652)
$ac \rightarrow rb$ (or $x \rightarrow y$)	0.069 (0.055, 0.083)	0.069 (0.056, 0.082)	0.011 (0.000, 0.025)	0.009 (0.000, 0.020)

Table S5: Posterior means and 95% HPD CIs of introgression probabilities (φ), introgression times (τ) and Bayes factors in support of gene flow (B_{10}) in the BPP analysis of the *Drosophila* data under the MSC-I model with $w \rightarrow z$ and $x \rightarrow y$ introgressions, and bidirectional introgression between extant species X and Y

Introgression	First half (1389 loci)			Second half (1388 loci)			
	$\hat{\varphi}$	$\hat{\tau}$	B_{10}	$\hat{\varphi}$	$\hat{\tau}$	B_{10}	B_{10}
<i>X = D. obscura</i> and <i>Y = D. pseudoobscura</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7461 (0.6968, 0.7990)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0387)	∞	0.7029 (0.6738, 0.7313)	0.0387 (0.0381, 0.0392)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0669 (0.0522, 0.0818)	0.0258 (0.0253, 0.0262)	∞	0.0671 (0.0545, 0.0803)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0011 (0.0000, 0.0034)	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0014)	0.01	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0028)	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0017)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0014 (0.0000, 0.0036)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)			0.01
<i>X = D. bifasciata</i> and <i>Y = D. pseudoobscura</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7345 (0.7005, 0.7683)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7014 (0.6714, 0.7311)	0.0387 (0.0381, 0.0392)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0675 (0.0534, 0.0820)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0672 (0.0547, 0.0803)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0262)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0027)	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0014)	0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0026)	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0017)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0014 (0.0000, 0.0035)		0.01	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0022)			0.01
<i>X = D. obscura</i> and <i>Y = D. persimilis</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7215 (0.6838, 0.7579)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7000 (0.6592, 0.7331)	0.0386 (0.0380, 0.0392)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0659 (0.0520, 0.0804)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0670 (0.0543, 0.0800)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0011 (0.0000, 0.0033)	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0014)	0.01	0.0011 (0.0000, 0.0034)	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0017)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0015 (0.0000, 0.0037)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)			0.01
<i>X = D. bifasciata</i> and <i>Y = D. persimilis</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7338 (0.6977, 0.7686)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7064 (0.6776, 0.7353)	0.0386 (0.0381, 0.0392)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0673 (0.0532, 0.0822)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0669 (0.0543, 0.0803)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0262)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0029)	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0014)	0.01	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0027)	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0017)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0014 (0.0000, 0.0035)		0.01	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)			0.01
<i>X = D. obscura</i> and <i>Y = D. miranda</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7239 (0.6740, 0.7688)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7023 (0.6720, 0.7315)	0.0386 (0.0380, 0.0392)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0662 (0.0524, 0.0810)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0676 (0.0550, 0.0809)	0.0256 (0.0252, 0.0260)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0010 (0.0000, 0.0031)	0.0023 (0.0001, 0.0041)	0.01	0.0010 (0.0000, 0.0030)	0.0020 (0.0000, 0.0039)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0014 (0.0000, 0.0037)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)			0.01
<i>X = D. bifasciata</i> and <i>Y = D. miranda</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7198 (0.6858, 0.7546)	0.0379 (0.0373, 0.0385)	∞	0.7057 (0.6768, 0.7351)	0.0387 (0.0381, 0.0393)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0669 (0.0528, 0.0818)	0.0257 (0.0252, 0.0261)	∞	0.0675 (0.0547, 0.0806)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0262)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0028)	0.0022 (0.0002, 0.0041)	0.01	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0028)	0.0020 (0.0000, 0.0039)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0014 (0.0000, 0.0035)		0.01	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)			0.01
<i>X = D. obscura</i> and <i>Y = D. lowei</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7134 (0.6762, 0.7523)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7220 (0.6902, 0.7524)	0.0387 (0.0381, 0.0393)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0654 (0.0512, 0.0798)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0679 (0.0550, 0.0811)	0.0258 (0.0254, 0.0262)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0025)	0.0056 (0.0006, 0.0102)	0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0025)	0.0057 (0.0006, 0.0103)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0014 (0.0000, 0.0039)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0025)			0.01
<i>X = D. bifasciata</i> and <i>Y = D. lowei</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7132 (0.6705, 0.7559)	0.0379 (0.0373, 0.0385)	∞	0.7178 (0.6868, 0.7473)	0.0387 (0.0381, 0.0393)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0662 (0.0522, 0.0811)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0678 (0.0547, 0.0807)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0262)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)	0.0048 (0.0000, 0.0094)	0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)	0.0051 (0.0000, 0.0097)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0014 (0.0000, 0.0036)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)			0.01
<i>X = D. obscura</i> and <i>Y = D. azteca</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7113 (0.6768, 0.7461)	0.0379 (0.0373, 0.0385)	∞	0.6967 (0.6681, 0.7249)	0.0387 (0.0381, 0.0392)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0661 (0.0521, 0.0807)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0672 (0.0546, 0.0802)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0262)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0025)	0.0058 (0.0005, 0.0103)	0.01	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0024)	0.0051 (0.0003, 0.0100)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0010 (0.0000, 0.0030)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)			0.01
<i>X = D. bifasciata</i> and <i>Y = D. azteca</i>							
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7279 (0.6892, 0.7691)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7042 (0.6760, 0.7323)	0.0387 (0.0381, 0.0392)	∞	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0669 (0.0527, 0.0813)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0671 (0.0543, 0.0799)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)	0.0054 (0.0005, 0.0103)	0.01	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)	0.0050 (0.0003, 0.0099)	0.01	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)			0.01

Introgression	First half (1389 loci)			Second half (1388 loci)		
	$\hat{\phi}$	$\hat{\tau}$	B_{10}	$\hat{\phi}$	$\hat{\tau}$	B_{10}
<i>X = D. obscura</i> and <i>Y = D. athabasca</i>						
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7299 (0.6866, 0.7747)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7257 (0.6960, 0.7545)	0.0387 (0.0381, 0.0393)	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0669 (0.0527, 0.0815)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0694 (0.0562, 0.0825)	0.0256 (0.0252, 0.0260)	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0025)	0.0033 (0.0002, 0.0063)	0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)	0.0031 (0.0000, 0.0059)	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0026)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0026)		0.01
<i>X = D. bifasciata</i> and <i>Y = D. athabasca</i>						
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7311 (0.6882, 0.7832)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7018 (0.6735, 0.7318)	0.0387 (0.0381, 0.0392)	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0669 (0.0525, 0.0814)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0673 (0.0545, 0.0802)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0262)	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)	0.0032 (0.0001, 0.0061)	0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0025)	0.0027 (0.0000, 0.0058)	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)		0.01	0.0010 (0.0000, 0.0029)		0.01
<i>X = D. obscura</i> and <i>Y = D. affinis</i>						
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7385 (0.7017, 0.7781)	0.0381 (0.0375, 0.0387)	∞	0.7020 (0.6736, 0.7300)	0.0386 (0.0381, 0.0392)	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0675 (0.0529, 0.0821)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0262)	∞	0.0669 (0.0541, 0.0799)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0027)	0.0001 (0.0000, 0.0002)	0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0026)	0.0001 (0.0000, 0.0003)	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0026)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)		0.01
<i>X = D. bifasciata</i> and <i>Y = D. affinis</i>						
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7139 (0.6794, 0.7487)	0.0379 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7026 (0.6750, 0.7295)	0.0386 (0.0381, 0.0392)	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0665 (0.0523, 0.0812)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞	0.0671 (0.0545, 0.0803)	0.0258 (0.0253, 0.0262)	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0025)	0.0000 (0.0000, 0.0001)	0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0025)	0.0002 (0.0000, 0.0004)	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0022)		0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0026)		0.01
<i>X = D. lowei</i> , <i>Y = D. azteca</i> , <i>Z = D. affinis</i>						
$w \rightarrow z$	0.7248 (0.6826, 0.7677)	0.0380 (0.0374, 0.0386)	∞	0.7061 (0.6767, 0.7348)	0.0388 (0.0382, 0.0394)	∞
$x \rightarrow y$	0.0671 (0.0530, 0.0817)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0260)	∞	0.0684 (0.0557, 0.0815)	0.0257 (0.0253, 0.0261)	∞
$X \rightarrow Y$	0.0028 (0.0002, 0.0060)	0.0055 (0.0020, 0.0081)	0.01	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0028)	0.0073 (0.0070, 0.0075)	0.01
$Y \rightarrow X$	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)		0.01	0.0019 (0.0000, 0.0046)		0.01
$X \rightarrow Z$	0.0022 (0.0000, 0.0054)	0.0026 (0.0003, 0.0058)	0.01	0.0010 (0.0000, 0.0032)	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0035)	0.01
$Z \rightarrow X$	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)		0.01	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)		0.01

Note.— All tested gene flow events between extant species are rejected when the model already accounts for the $w \rightarrow z$ and $x \rightarrow y$ introgressions.

Table S6: Posterior means and 95% HPD CIs (in parentheses) obtained in BPP analyses of the real data under the JC and GTR mutation models

Model	JC		GTR	
	First half	Second half	First half	Second half
MSC-I				
$\varphi_{w \rightarrow z}$	0.728 (0.689, 0.769)	0.712 (0.681, 0.743)	0.723 (0.688, 0.758)	0.708 (0.675, 0.739)
$\varphi_{x \rightarrow y}$	0.069 (0.055, 0.083)	0.069 (0.056, 0.082)	0.067 (0.053, 0.081)	0.069 (0.056, 0.082)
MSC-M				
$M_{w \rightarrow z}$	0.568 (0.518, 0.615)	0.603 (0.555, 0.652)	0.568 (0.523, 0.614)	0.605 (0.555, 0.654)
$M_{x \rightarrow y}$	0.011 (0.000, 0.025)	0.009 (0.000, 0.020)	0.008 (0.000, 0.018)	0.007 (0.000, 0.016)

Note.— Estimates of τ_s and θ_s are shown in figure S2.

Table S7: Parameter estimates (posterior means and 95% HPD CIs) and Bayes factors (B_{10}) for testing gene flow in BPP analysis of triplet and quintet datasets informative for $D. lowei \leftrightarrow D. affinis$ gene flow

Parameter	$X = D. pseudoobscura$		$X = D. persimilis$		$X = D. miranda$	
	Estimate	B_{10}	Estimate	B_{10}	Estimate	B_{10}
Triplet tree: $((X, D. lowei), D. affinis)$						
$\hat{\varphi}_{p \rightarrow q}$ ($D. lowei \rightarrow D. affinis$)	0.0477 (0.0326, 0.0630)	∞	0.0478 (0.0333, 0.0631)	∞	0.0420 (0.0307, 0.0537)	∞
$\hat{\varphi}_{q \rightarrow p}$ ($D. affinis \rightarrow D. lowei$)	0.0089 (0.0000, 0.0186)	0.01	0.0046 (0.0000, 0.0130)	0.01	0.0010 (0.0000, 0.0029)	0.01
τ_b	0.0198 (0.0193, 0.0202)		0.0192 (0.0187, 0.0196)		0.0199 (0.0195, 0.0203)	
τ_e	0.0085 (0.0083, 0.0088)		0.0086 (0.0083, 0.0088)		0.0084 (0.0082, 0.0086)	
$\tau_p = \tau_q$	0.0082 (0.0074, 0.0087)		0.0081 (0.0072, 0.0087)		0.0081 (0.0074, 0.0086)	
$\theta_{D. lowei}$	0.0136 (0.0013, 0.0293)		0.0134 (0.0012, 0.0292)		0.0150 (0.0016, 0.0320)	
$\theta_{D. affinis}$	0.0147 (0.0018, 0.0298)		0.0143 (0.0005, 0.0307)		0.0109 (0.0002, 0.0260)	
θ_b	0.0609 (0.0587, 0.0631)		0.0662 (0.0639, 0.0686)		0.0458 (0.0439, 0.0476)	
θ_e	0.0221 (0.0206, 0.0236)		0.0229 (0.0213, 0.0245)		0.0130 (0.0122, 0.0137)	
Quintet tree: $((X, D. lowei), D. affinis), (D. obscura, D. guanche)$						
$\hat{\varphi}_{p \rightarrow q}$ ($D. lowei \rightarrow D. affinis$)	0.0148 (0.0069, 0.0232)	0.08	0.0231 (0.0132, 0.0332)	6.21	0.0169 (0.0093, 0.0246)	0.35
$\hat{\varphi}_{q \rightarrow p}$ ($D. affinis \rightarrow D. lowei$)	0.0010 (0.0000, 0.0030)	0.01	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0026)	0.01	0.0008 (0.0000, 0.0024)	0.01
τ_r	0.0298 (0.0295, 0.0301)		0.0295 (0.0292, 0.0299)		0.0301 (0.0298, 0.0304)	
τ_a	0.0208 (0.0202, 0.0214)		0.0208 (0.0202, 0.0215)		0.0214 (0.0207, 0.0221)	
τ_b	0.0207 (0.0203, 0.0210)		0.0204 (0.0199, 0.0208)		0.0206 (0.0202, 0.0209)	
τ_e	0.0093 (0.0090, 0.0095)		0.0093 (0.0090, 0.0095)		0.0090 (0.0088, 0.0092)	
$\tau_p = \tau_q$	0.0086 (0.0072, 0.0095)		0.0089 (0.0079, 0.0095)		0.0085 (0.0074, 0.0092)	
$\theta_{D. lowei}$	0.0137 (0.0012, 0.0296)		0.0145 (0.0015, 0.0309)		0.0144 (0.0014, 0.0308)	
$\theta_{D. affinis}$	0.0114 (0.0003, 0.0271)		0.0115 (0.0003, 0.0273)		0.0112 (0.0003, 0.0266)	
θ_r	0.0762 (0.0742, 0.0782)		0.0785 (0.0764, 0.0805)		0.0662 (0.0644, 0.0680)	
θ_a	0.0743 (0.0646, 0.0843)		0.0702 (0.0611, 0.0796)		0.0838 (0.0714, 0.0966)	
θ_b	0.0461 (0.0428, 0.0495)		0.0500 (0.0462, 0.0537)		0.0307 (0.0285, 0.0328)	
θ_e	0.0216 (0.0202, 0.0229)		0.0229 (0.0214, 0.0244)		0.0128 (0.0121, 0.0136)	
Quintet tree: $((X, D. lowei), D. affinis), (D. obscura, D. guanche)$, with $w \rightarrow z$ and $x \rightarrow y$ introgressions						
$\hat{\varphi}_{w \rightarrow z}$	0.9066 (0.8931, 0.9196)	∞	0.8750 (0.8600, 0.8901)	∞	0.9513 (0.9405, 0.9621)	∞
$\hat{\varphi}_{x \rightarrow y}$	0.0890 (0.0754, 0.1031)	∞	0.0851 (0.0717, 0.0981)	∞	0.0913 (0.0764, 0.1063)	∞
$\hat{\varphi}_{p \rightarrow q}$ ($D. lowei \rightarrow D. affinis$)	0.0413 (0.0273, 0.0555)	∞	0.0571 (0.0418, 0.0723)	∞	0.0496 (0.0365, 0.0629)	∞
$\hat{\varphi}_{q \rightarrow p}$ ($D. affinis \rightarrow D. lowei$)	0.0009 (0.0000, 0.0027)	0.01	0.0010 (0.0000, 0.0031)	0.01	0.0007 (0.0000, 0.0023)	0.01
τ_r	0.0902 (0.0852, 0.0949)		0.0818 (0.0795, 0.0841)		0.0872 (0.0837, 0.0906)	
τ_a	0.0225 (0.0222, 0.0229)		0.0225 (0.0221, 0.0229)		0.0234 (0.0230, 0.0238)	
τ_b	0.0205 (0.0200, 0.0209)		0.0205 (0.0201, 0.0210)		0.0210 (0.0205, 0.0214)	
τ_e	0.0090 (0.0088, 0.0093)		0.0090 (0.0087, 0.0092)		0.0088 (0.0086, 0.0090)	
$\tau_w = \tau_z$	0.0356 (0.0351, 0.0360)		0.0353 (0.0348, 0.0357)		0.0352 (0.0348, 0.0357)	
$\tau_x = \tau_y$	0.0225 (0.0221, 0.0228)		0.0224 (0.0220, 0.0228)		0.0233 (0.0229, 0.0237)	
$\tau_p = \tau_q$	0.0088 (0.0084, 0.0093)		0.0088 (0.0085, 0.0092)		0.0087 (0.0083, 0.0090)	
$\theta_{D. obscura}$	0.0018 (0.0001, 0.0042)		0.0013 (0.0000, 0.0029)		0.0011 (0.0001, 0.0025)	
$\theta_{D. lowei}$	0.0149 (0.0013, 0.0316)		0.0148 (0.0015, 0.0317)		0.0149 (0.0017, 0.0319)	
$\theta_{D. affinis}$	0.0116 (0.0003, 0.0273)		0.0118 (0.0003, 0.0277)		0.0112 (0.0002, 0.0266)	
θ_r	0.1228 (0.1130, 0.1333)		0.1130 (0.1049, 0.1211)		0.1183 (0.1071, 0.1299)	
θ_a	0.0493 (0.0475, 0.0512)		0.0483 (0.0464, 0.0501)		0.0491 (0.0473, 0.0508)	
θ_b	0.0476 (0.0447, 0.0505)		0.0510 (0.0479, 0.0543)		0.0305 (0.0284, 0.0325)	
θ_e	0.0221 (0.0207, 0.0235)		0.0237 (0.0222, 0.0253)		0.0134 (0.0126, 0.0142)	
θ_w	$= \theta_a$		$= \theta_a$		$= \theta_a$	
θ_z	$= \theta_b$		$= \theta_b$		$= \theta_b$	
θ_x	$= \theta_{D. obscura}$		$= \theta_{D. obscura}$		$= \theta_{D. obscura}$	
θ_y	$= \theta_b$		$= \theta_b$		$= \theta_b$	
θ_p	$= \theta_{D. lowei}$		$= \theta_{D. lowei}$		$= \theta_{D. lowei}$	
θ_q	$= \theta_{D. affinis}$		$= \theta_{D. affinis}$		$= \theta_{D. affinis}$	

Note.— Nodes r, a, b, e, p, q refer to the species tree in figure 1a. The triplet species tree is $((X, D. lowei), D. affinis)$, where X is $D. pseudoobscura, D. persimilis,$ or $D. miranda$, with species divergences at nodes b and e and with bidirectional introgression at nodes p, q (Fig. 1a). The quintet datasets include two outgroup species $D. guanche$ and $D. obscura$, with an additional internal node a (Fig. 1a). The quartet introgression model assumes the $w \rightarrow z$ and $x \rightarrow y$ introgressions (as in Fig. 1b). The number of loci in the triplet datasets is 2672, 2646, and 2672 for $X = D. pseudoobscura, D. persimilis,$ and $D. miranda$, respectively, and the corresponding numbers for the quintet datasets are 2759, 2757, and 2758.

Table S8: Posterior means and 95% HPD CIs (in parentheses) from **BPP** analysis of datasets simulated under the **MSC-I** and **MSC-M** models of figure 1b with the *D. insularis* outgroup

Parameters	MSC-I			MSC-M		
	Truth	Estimates, first half	Estimates, second half	Truth	Estimates, first half	Estimates, second half
Population sizes (θ , $\times 10^{-2}$)						
θ_o	17.95	17.61 (16.79, 18.44)	17.53 (16.72, 18.36)	18.06	17.85 (17.02, 18.69)	17.28 (16.44, 18.06)
θ_r	11.39	10.94 (9.18, 12.69)	11.30 (9.88, 12.73)	6.99	1.83 (0.17, 4.03)	1.73 (0.15, 3.78)
θ_a	5.14	5.13 (4.86, 5.40)	5.17 (4.89, 5.46)	4.81	4.65 (4.42, 4.87)	4.88 (4.65, 5.11)
θ_b	7.20	7.15 (6.62, 7.68)	6.64 (6.16, 7.13)	6.83	6.71 (6.27, 7.15)	6.49 (6.05, 6.96)
θ_c	4.50	3.53 (2.63, 4.43)	3.50 (2.44, 4.60)	4.55	4.19 (3.04, 5.40)	5.19 (3.90, 6.53)
θ_d	1.72	1.84 (1.69, 2.00)	1.72 (1.58, 1.86)	1.73	1.79 (1.64, 1.94)	1.82 (1.67, 1.98)
θ_e	3.72	3.82 (3.51, 4.14)	4.02 (3.70, 4.33)	3.72	3.87 (3.56, 4.18)	3.68 (3.39, 3.98)
θ_f	1.57	1.57 (1.44, 1.69)	1.55 (1.42, 1.67)	1.58	1.48 (1.36, 1.60)	1.61 (1.48, 1.74)
θ_g	1.11	0.96 (0.66, 1.26)	1.27 (0.97, 1.58)	1.10	1.08 (0.77, 1.40)	1.03 (0.75, 1.32)
θ_h	1.92	1.89 (1.66, 2.13)	1.70 (1.48, 1.92)	1.92	1.95 (1.69, 2.21)	2.04 (1.79, 2.29)
θ_i	1.46	1.69 (1.16, 2.22)	1.75 (1.26, 2.24)	1.46	1.68 (1.26, 2.13)	1.13 (0.70, 1.61)
θ_w	= θ_a			–	–	–
θ_z	= θ_b			–	–	–
θ_x	= θ_c			–	–	–
θ_y	= θ_b			–	–	–
Speciation/introgression times (τ , $\times 10^{-2}$)						
τ_o	9.54	9.57 (9.39, 9.75)	9.67 (9.49, 9.84)	9.51	9.37 (9.20, 9.53)	9.63 (9.47, 9.78)
τ_r	7.53	7.78 (7.40, 8.17)	7.37 (6.97, 7.77)	8.77	9.32 (9.09, 9.54)	9.60 (9.41, 9.78)
τ_a	2.75	2.78 (2.72, 2.84)	2.73 (2.68, 2.79)	2.74	2.69 (2.63, 2.74)	2.73 (2.68, 2.78)
τ_b	2.18	2.20 (2.15, 2.26)	2.24 (2.19, 2.30)	2.20	2.19 (2.14, 2.24)	2.24 (2.18, 2.29)
τ_c	1.96	2.07 (1.95, 2.20)	2.11 (1.97, 2.26)	1.95	1.98 (1.84, 2.12)	1.90 (1.75, 2.04)
τ_d	1.03	1.00 (0.96, 1.05)	1.02 (0.98, 1.06)	1.02	1.01 (0.97, 1.06)	1.03 (0.98, 1.07)
τ_e	1.01	1.01 (0.96, 1.06)	0.97 (0.92, 1.02)	1.01	0.98 (0.93, 1.03)	1.01 (0.96, 1.05)
τ_f	0.75	0.76 (0.71, 0.81)	0.77 (0.72, 0.81)	0.74	0.77 (0.72, 0.81)	0.72 (0.67, 0.77)
τ_g	0.63	0.66 (0.59, 0.73)	0.60 (0.53, 0.66)	0.63	0.64 (0.58, 0.71)	0.66 (0.59, 0.72)
τ_h	0.41	0.41 (0.37, 0.45)	0.43 (0.39, 0.46)	0.41	0.42 (0.38, 0.46)	0.39 (0.35, 0.43)
τ_i	0.15	0.12 (0.06, 0.17)	0.11 (0.06, 0.16)	0.15	0.10 (0.05, 0.15)	0.17 (0.12, 0.23)
$\tau_{w \rightarrow z}$	4.00	4.04 (3.96, 4.12)	4.01 (3.93, 4.09)	–	–	–
$\tau_{x \rightarrow y}$	2.73	2.75 (2.68, 2.81)	2.69 (2.60, 2.77)	–	–	–
Gene-flow rate		Introgression probability (φ)		Migration rate (M)		
$ra \rightarrow rb$ (or $w \rightarrow z$)	0.708	0.716 (0.686, 0.747)	0.712 (0.680, 0.744)	0.557	0.500 (0.457, 0.544)	0.524 (0.472, 0.571)
$ac \rightarrow rb$ (or $x \rightarrow y$)	0.098	0.119 (0.094, 0.144)	0.090 (0.068, 0.112)	0.016	0.023 (0.002, 0.048)	0.033 (0.002, 0.068)

Note.— True parameter values for the MSC-I model with $w \rightarrow z$ and $x \rightarrow y$ introgressions are from table S2 (first half with the *D. insularis* outgroup), and the parameter values for the MSC-M model are from table S3. Node o is the root of the species tree including the outgroup.

Table S9: Posterior means and 95% HPD CIs (in parentheses) for the rate of gene flow (φ in MSC-I or M in MSC-M) obtained in **BPP** analyses of the simulated data using the 0.1x, 1x and 10x priors

Model	Truth	Priors on τ and θ		
		0.1x	1x	10x
MSC-I				
$\varphi_{w \rightarrow z}$	0.708	0.761 (0.734, 0.788)	0.716 (0.686, 0.747)	0.719 (0.688, 0.750)
$\varphi_{x \rightarrow y}$	0.098	0.123 (0.099, 0.147)	0.119 (0.094, 0.144)	0.119 (0.094, 0.143)
MSC-M				
$M_{w \rightarrow z}$	0.557	0.499 (0.458, 0.545)	0.500 (0.457, 0.544)	0.509 (0.465, 0.554)
$M_{x \rightarrow y}$	0.016	0.024 (0.001, 0.051)	0.023 (0.002, 0.048)	0.024 (0.001, 0.051)

Note.— Estimates of τ s and θ s are shown in figure S3. See legend to figure S3.